

Younes & Soraya Nazarian Library
University of Haifa

אוניברסיטת חיפה
UNIVERSITY OF HAIFA
جامعة حيفا

The Copyright Chain in the Digital Curation Process

The “Which Copyright” Project at the Nazarian Library, University of Haifa

Keren Barner

Digital Projects & Special Collections
Younes & Soraya Nazarian Library, University of Haifa

Why is this project worth talking about?

The need for such a project is emphasized in this era of accessible internet, open access movement, image sharing platforms and mostly - the rise of AI.

Assessing and capturing appropriate copyrights for a large volume of items

Moderated access and licenses for the reuse of collections by memory institutes

A crucial step in the broader curation workflow for any GLAM institutes

Good research needs good data

What drove us to take action?

Photo Andreas Meyer

What drove us to take action?

Judith

SOPHIA LOREN

PETER FINCH JACK HAWKINS

Theatrical release poster by Michel Landi

Directed by	Daniel Mann
Written by	John Michael Hayes
Story by	Lawrence Durrell
Produced by	Kurt Unger
Starring	Sophia Loren Peter Finch Jack Hawkins
Cinematography	John Wilcox
Edited by	Peter Taylor
Music by	Sol Kaplan
Distributed by	Paramount Pictures
Release date	20 January 1966 (US)
Running time	109 minutes
Countries	Israel United Kingdom United States
Language	English

The Framework's Building blocks

Nazarian Library, 2024

Demonstrating a cohesive approach to managing digital collections responsibly and ethically

Cultural Heritage Image Sharing Recommendations Report
(Knazook and Murphy, 2023)

A workflow to publish Collections as Data: the case of Cultural Heritage data spaces
(Candela et al., 2023)

Finding the balance between respecting copyright laws and promoting open access to cultural heritage

**WorldFair
Recommendations**

**A workflow to publish
Collections as Data**

“Which Copyright” Project

Key Elements

Matching workflow steps

Implementation

**Commitment to
FAIR principles**

**Clear licensing
standards**

**Encouraging
Open Access**

**Ethical sharing
practices**

**WorldFair
Recommendations**

Key Elements

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**A workflow to publish
Collections as Data**

Matching workflow steps

[4]
Use a public platform

[10]
Develop a portal page

“Which Copyright” Project

Implementation

Active Open Access
promotion policies

Collections are openly
accessible in the library’s
portal.

Active contributions to
social platforms:
**Wikimedia / Wikipedia /
Wikidata**

**WorldFair
Recommendations**

Key Elements

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standards**

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Open Access**

**Ethical sharing
practices**

**A workflow to publish
Collections as Data**

Matching workflow steps

Add 'Terms of Use'

“Which Copyright” Project

Implementation

- Regular updates to 'Terms of Use' to reflect changes in copyright laws.
- Attaching copyright licenses can mitigate the AI-related risks, by ensuring legal use and protecting the intellectual property of cultural institutions.

Workflow Action Points

Workflow Action Points

Assessment of digital collections scope and selecting which collections will be addressed in this process

Workflow Action Points

Explore options for adding copyright licenses within ALMA digital object management system

Workflow Action Points

Preparation of data sheet for selected collections with updated copyholders details and new signed licenses

Workflow Action Points

Preparation of collections records sets with digital representation

Workflow Action Points

Update records with new copyright information

Workflow Action Points

Update Records with new fields for: "How to Credit".

Workflow Action Points

WIKI pilot: Contributions to Wiki platforms:
Wikimedia, Wikipedia, Wikidata

Outcomes

The project was meant to span two years: 2024-2025
 Over 70% was achieved by November 2024

Outcomes

Most items are now available under the permissive CC BY 4.0 license

Outcomes

Numerous contributions to Wiki platforms

Wikimedia Commons: 210 images | Wikipedia: 100 values

Wikidata: 20 files | Wikibase Timna: 19 inputs

The introduction of Book of Esther, hand written, part of Cairo Gniza, digital collections of Younes & Soraya Nazarian Library, University of Haifa

Special page

Search media

timna nazarian library

Images Audio Video Other Media Categories and Pages

License File Type Image size Community Assessments Sort by: Relevance

Hot springs in Tiberias 1924, Younes & Soraya Nazarian library, University of Haifa digital collections

Tiberias main road, 1925, Younes & Soraya Library digital collections, University of Haifa

The Final Result

Search

Copyright Notice

Image

IMAGE

סופיה לורן בתפקיד יהודית : Sophia Loren as Judith / צלם: אנדריאס מאייר

מאייר, אנדריאס, 1921-2016 - צלם; אוסף אנדריאס מאייר

1964

FULL TEXT

[Sign in to your User Account](#)

Sources for Reading, Listening, and Display:

/ סופיה לורן בתפקיד יהודית 1 ITEM[S] (JPG, 2.28 MB)

© All rights reserved

The Final Result

Search

Copyright Notice

Image

The Younes and Soraya Nazarian Library | University of Haifa

צלם: אנדריאס מאייר / סופיה לורן בתפקיד יהודית / Sophia Loren as Judith = סופיה לורן בתפקיד יהודית

Copyright Statement

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URI: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

CONFIRM

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Image

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צלם: אנדריאס מאייר / סופיה לורן בתפקיד יהודית / Sophia Loren as Judith = סופיה לורן בתפקיד יהודית

Photo Andreas Meyer

» Description

Title:
סופיה לורן בתפקיד יהודית = Sophia Loren as Judith /
צלם: אנדריאס מאייר

Author:
מאייר, אנדריאס, 1921-2016 - צלם
אוסף אנדריאס מאייר

Subjects:
Loren, Sophia, 1934-;
Meyer, Andreas, 1921-;
Motion pictures, American -- History;
Women in motion pictures;
Motion pictures -- United States -- History -- 20th
century;
Motion pictures -- Israel -- History -- 20th century;
Motion pictures -- Great Britain -- History -- 20th
century;
Arab-Israeli conflict -- 1948-1967;
Israel -- History -- War of Independence, 1948-1949
-- Motion pictures and the war;
Eretz Israel -- History -- 1945-1948

Content/Description:
How to credit: From the Digital Collection of Younes
& Sorya Nazarian library, University of Haifa
2020 ; האוסף התקבל בספריית אוניברסיטת חיפה בקיץ
2020 ; האוסף זורה ותוארך על ידי התורם.

Language:
Hebrew

Notes:
מקור: תצלום; רוני קניגסברג

Lessons learned

Start on a smaller scale

Thoroughly examine copyright matters
when acquiring a new collection

Update contact details of collection owners annually, to maintain up-to-date records

Revise licenses yearly to align with legal developments and emerging copyright law

Establish a dedicated team to identify projects and channels for collection sharing

Regularly seek updates by reading, consulting experts and actively participating in international groups, conferences and forums

Cultivate a passion for the work. Enthusiasm is a critical driver for success.

Insights

Deeper Understanding

The project helped us not only in terms of copyright management but also in gaining a deeper understanding of the scope and composition of our collections and its valuable for researchers.

Standardization

The project prompted us to upgrade our collections to meet international standards, transforming our digital collection to datasets for better reuse.

Challenges

Navigating as librarians without formal legal training through the complexities of copyright law and mediate it to copyrights holders.

Motivation & Creativity

The whole process boosted our team's professional pride and motivation for learning new terms and skills. It increased motivation to collaborate with local and global organizations and initiatives

We are seeking to collaborate and share our experience with you.

Please feel free to contact me directly
kbarner@univ.haifa.ac.il

Younes & Soraya Nazarian Library
University of Haifa

COLLECTION
Geography & Cartography

COLLECTION
Ilanot project: Kabbalistic diagrams

COLLECTION
Archives Museums & Research Institutes

COLLECTION
Performing Arts

COLLECTION
Hebrew Manuscripts

COLLECTION
Archaeology

COLLECTION
Fragments of the Cairo Geniza

COLLECTION
The Joel Leavitt Collection - China in 1979

COLLECTION
Ezra Nejat-Chaim Archive

COLLECTION
The Sign Language Research Lab

COLLECTION
Nurit Bird-David - Anthropological study of the Nayaka hunter-gatherers

COLLECTION
Digital Heritage Archive of Egyptian Jewry

COLLECTION
Photographers

COLLECTION
Safed Archive

Thank you